

D1.3 Initial plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

Authors:

Francesca Watson - SINTEF

Simon Clark – SINTEF

Olav Spanne – SINTEF

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Executive Summary

DigiBatt aims to reduce time and cost of battery testing using streamlined digital approaches for data exchange, virtual and hybrid testing methods and strategies for intelligent design of experiments. Methods developed in the project will be made available for the whole battery community to utilise. To maximise the impact of the work and ensure that relevant stakeholders are aware of advances made, it is crucial that information about the project and its outcomes are communicated to a variety of audiences in a targeted way.

This document describes the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan for the DigiBatt HEU project. Communication activities will be analysed before being undertaken, according to the Why?, Who?, What?, How? model. Activities will be evaluated to ensure that effective communication is maintained throughout the project.

Communication in DigiBatt can be broken down into three phases: Awareness phase M0 - M12 where we will make people aware of the project and expected outputs, Sharing phase M13 - M24 where will disseminate project results and assess market potential of outputs. Use phase M25 - M36 where we will disseminate results widely and begin implementation of results in industrial settings.

Key stakeholders and associated key messages to be communicated have been identified, along with appropriate communication channels.

Preliminary plans for exploitation include public software releases, enhanced by publicly available examples, demos and tutorial code.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
WP	Work package
KPI	Key performance indicator
EO	Expected outcome
EI	Expected impact
SoMe	Social media

1. Introduction

DigiBatt is a 3 year Horizon Europe project which will establish a novel, open, multi-scale digital toolbox to accelerate the testing and development of batteries. By STANDARDIZING, AUTOMATING, and ACCELERATING the battery testing process, DigiBatt will streamline testing workflows, improve the quality of results, and make digital battery testing accessible for the entire battery community. DigiBatt will realise these ambitious goals through:

- Universal, interoperable, semantic data models for battery data and metadata
- Digital twin infrastructure to link experimental testing and parameterisation with model-based virtual testing
- Strategies for intelligent design of experiments to reduce the number and duration of battery tests
- Reliable tools for predicting battery lifetime and safety within system-level infrastructure

To maximise the impact of the work and ensure that relevant stakeholders are aware of advances made, it is crucial that information about the project and its outcomes are communicated to a variety of audiences in a targeted way.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document sets out the initial plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication of activities within DigiBatt. It explains the principles which should be used when deciding what information should be shared, how it should be shared and with whom. This document will be used as a starting point for dissemination, exploitation and communication activities within DigiBatt. We will assess planned measures during the lifetime of the project and ensure that we are only carrying activities which we believe will maximise impact.

1.2 Intended readership

In the project:

- All project participants who will communicate, disseminate or exploit work from the project.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

This deliverable is not a fixed document but will evolve during the lifespan of the project.

Deliverable D1.3 is the initial plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities.

Deliverable D1.7 is the Final plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, due month 36. This will contain a more detailed plan for how we will continue to maximise the impact of the project after it has finished.

1.4 Responsibility for activities

In DigiBatt, research and project dissemination, exploitation and communication are the responsibility of all partners. Efforts will be coordinated by the project coordinator SINTEF as part of WP1. The Communication Department at SINTEF Industry shall assist the project with user-focused and research communication, as well as quality assurance and the preparation of communication plans.

2. Overall communication strategy

DigiBatt's goals are to standardize, automate, and accelerate battery testing processes using advanced digital techniques. DigiBatt targets a 30% reduction in the time and 20% reduction in the cost of battery development. Thus contributing to the future of electric mobility and supporting the green transition.

The communication efforts aim to help the project achieve its goals by:

- Delivering and publishing high-quality research results
- Coordinating communication across the project
- Engaging with the EU, other EU projects, and the battery community in both industry and academia.
- Highlighting the importance of our research and battery research in general in the wider European and global society.

To achieve this, we need to implement the following communication strategies:

- Build trust and a strong reputation for the project.
- Ensure that information and communication are reliable and coordinated (with SINTEF responsible as coordinator)
- Ensure that information and communication are consistent, unified, with regular frequency, and of good quality.
- Communicate and inform effectively to reach the target audiences
- Adapt messages to different target groups and channels
- Contribute to a good internal workflow and knowledge sharing within the project
- Ensure that the results of communication efforts are measured, and continuously evaluated.

In DigiBatt we will follow a general communication model as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 DigiBatt communication model showing the things to be considered when disseminating and communicating information about the project.

2.1 DigiBatt communication phases

Communication in DigiBatt can be broken down into three phases which change as the project progresses, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 DigiBatt communication phases

3. Communication objectives

Figure 3 Pathway from DigiBatt Results to Expected Impacts

The overall purpose of dissemination, exploitation and communication in DigiBatt is to contribute to achieving the expected impacts as shown in Figure 3. These can only be achieved by effective dissemination and exploitation of key results to a variety of stakeholders leading to the expected outcomes of the project.

4. Key stakeholders

Key stakeholders in DigiBatt are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 DigiBatt stakeholders

Target group	Communication aims	Communication measures
General public	To promote general acceptance of sustainable battery technology. To promote EU funded research activities across a wide spectrum of society.	DigiBatt will spread information aimed at a general audience via social media campaigns and podcasts, videos to communicate the impact of an efficient and sustainable battery chain on end-users and the benefit of carrying out collaborative research projects in this area.
Research institutes and universities	To promote adoption of research results. To encourage external contributions to open-source software. To achieve wider, inter-disciplinary collaboration amongst researchers in the battery community.	Consortium members from various research institutes and universities will communicate about research results and project aims, plus opportunities to contribute and collaborate, via technical presentations to internal and external networks and attendance at relevant conferences.
Cell manufacturers	To encourage adoption of research results in industrial settings. To help identify future research and market needs specific to cell manufacturers.	Close collaboration with partner FREYR, the leading Norwegian cell manufacturer, will ensure results are communicated and that directions taken are specifically tailored to cell manufacturing requirements. We will communicate with other cell manufacturers to share results and gain insight into needs, via the project advisory board and externally organised stakeholder events.
Cell integrators	To encourage adoption of research results in industrial settings. To help identify future research and market needs specific to cell integrators.	Close collaboration with partners AVL and CORVUS will ensure that results are communicated and that directions taken are specifically tailored to cell integration. We will communicate with other cell integrators to share results and gain insight into needs, via the project advisory board and other stakeholder events.

Cell recyclers	To encourage adoption of research results in industrial settings. To help identify future research and market needs specific to cell recyclers.	Through close collaboration with battery networks and attendance at European wide battery meetings we will communicate the results of the project to leading cell recyclers in Europe. The project results will also be used to support 2 nd life battery assessments.
EU associations and policy makers	To stay aligned with relevant associations and policy initiatives across the wider battery community.	Through close collaboration with battery networks and attendance at European wide battery meetings we will communicate the results of the project to BEPA, the EBA, Batteries Europe, and Battery2030+.

5. Key messages

Key messages which we need to communicate and the relevant target groups for those messages are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 DigiBatt Key messages and corresponding target groups.

Key message		General Public	Researchers	Cell Manufacturers	Cell Integrators	Cell Recyclers	Policy makers
1	DigiBatt will make battery technology, cheaper, greener and safer by creating cutting-edge digital tools to speed up design, testing and manufacturing of new batteries.	x					x
2	DigiBatt will help achieve the EU's climate goals by reducing the resources, cost and time taken to develop and manufacture new batteries.	x					x
3	DigiBatt will make the European battery industry more competitive by creating advanced digital tools making them widely available to save European industry both time and money.	x					x
4	DigiBatt will help meet the EU's growing need for battery production by streamlining processes and making the European battery industry more sustainable and more competitive.	x					x
5	DigiBatt will accelerate research within the academic community by developing an open-source digital toolbox for standardised, automated and accelerated battery testing.		x				x
6	Cutting-edge simulation software, standard data models and frameworks developed in the		x	x	x	x	

	project will be available for free, for researchers in industry and academia to use and build upon in their own research.						
7	DigiBatt will develop digital tools which can improve and accelerate design, parameterisation and testing of new batteries. This allows manufacturers to streamline processes and make informed decisions based on state-of-the-art digital modelling.			x			
8	DigiBatt will develop new tools to automate testing protocols thus reducing time and costs for testing and increasing reliability of results.		x	x	x	x	
9	DigiBatt will develop advanced, digital, system-level models to automate and accelerate system-level testing. Including tools for Hardware-in-the-Loop testing.		x		x	x	
10	Tools developed in DigiBatt will allow for better traceability of batteries and better predictions of lifetime and safety parameters of specific batteries.		x	x	x	x	x

6. Dissemination and communication channels

Various channels for dissemination and communication are available to us throughout the project. These are aimed at different audiences. An assessment of target audience and most appropriate communication channels to use will be made for each item, prior to its dissemination / communication, thus ensuring maximum impact.

Figure 4 Target groups and affiliated channels used at SINTEF. We will also take advantage of communications channels used by other project partners as appropriate.

7. Dissemination and communication plan

Table 3 Dissemination and communication activities in DigiBatt

<p>Project identity, website and e-newsletter</p> <p>We have created a finalised DigiBatt identity including logos and templates which is available to all project partners. This will enable consistent communication and dissemination and ensure project results are easily linked back to the project itself. A DigiBatt website has been setup to inform interested parties about the consortium, project plans and results. All partners will be able to highlight activities and disseminate results through the e-newsletter which will be published twice a year. Each partner will submit a minimum of one post per year to be published on the website and sent out in the e-newsletter.</p>
<p>Dissemination materials</p> <p>Dissemination materials will be created to introduce the project to different audiences. This includes for example informative brochures, flyers and promotional materials for handing out at industry conferences. We will also create 3 videos, 1 per year, describing project ambitions and current results, to be shared on social media, for wide dissemination amongst interested parties and used as an introduction to the project at stakeholder events.</p>
<p>Wide impact media campaigns</p> <p>A DigiBatt LinkedIn page has been created. A press release was issued at the start of the project and further press releases will be issued when significant research results are published. Publications will be promoted on social media accounts and via the website and e-newsletter.</p>
<p>General public dissemination</p> <p>At least 3 events aimed at a general audience will be undertaken e.g. European researchers night (Europe-wide), and local public science events (e.g. Forskningsdagene in Norway, Pint of Science events across Europe). We will publish at least 1 podcast and at least 3 popular science articles to disseminate project results to the general public.</p>
<p>Specific battery industry events</p> <p>Results from DigiBatt will be disseminated at various events aimed at the European battery community e.g. AABC Europe, IMLB, European Battery Innovation Days.</p>
<p>DigiBatt symposia</p> <p>We will hold at least to 2 online symposia during the project to disseminate project results to relevant stakeholders within the battery community and encourage uptake of DigiBatt technologies beyond the consortium partners.</p>
<p>Linked events with other EU battery projects</p> <p>Several DigiBatt participants are involved in other European battery initiatives like BEPA, 2ZERO, BATT4EU and Battery 2030+. We will hold linked events with other</p>

projects to disseminate results widely throughout the European battery community and help find synergies between projects which can be exploited.

Peer reviewed, open access publications

Results from DigiBatt will be published as open source, peer reviewed, journal publications. The project will produce at least 15 articles published in leading scientific journals.

Conference presentations

DigiBatt results will be presented at least 10 national and international academic conferences.

Table 4 DigiBatt dissemination output summary

Communication and Dissemination output	Target audience	Style	KPIs
Website and e-newsletter	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General	Website online with content by M3 200 e-newsletter subscribers by M12
Brochure (hard copy / digital)	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General	Brochure created by M12 Copies distributed at 5 industry / academic events
Flyers	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General, technical	At least 6 flyers created throughout the project, 1 technical and 1 general per year.
Videos	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General	1 video per year created during the project.
Social media accounts	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General	At least 20 social media posts on LinkedIn. At least 1 post for each published paper and conference attendance.
Press releases	General public, Researchers, Industry stakeholders	General	1 press release at start of project. At least 3 press releases in total.
Podcast	General public	General	at least 1 podcast
Popular science articles and events	General public	General	At least 3 popular science articles

			At least 3 events aimed at a general audience
Battery stakeholder events (meetings / conferences / symposia)	Industry stakeholders	General, technical	At least 8 stakeholder events attended by consortium members including 2 DigiBatt symposia .
Scientific journal publications	Researchers	Technical	At least 15 articles published in leading scientific journals.
Academic conferences	Researchers, Industry stakeholders	Technical	At least 10 national and international academic conferences.

8. Exploitation Plan

The **DigiBatt** exploitation strategy (WP1) will address how to **generate value from the project results**. A project **Innovation Manager** (IM) will be appointed by the Project Coordinator to identify and oversee innovative project results with potential for exploitation. An exploitation strategy will be prepared to assess how the **DigiBatt** project results will be commercialized by relevant stakeholders, beyond the end of the project, and by using EC Horizon Results Platform. A preliminary list of exploitable results already identified are listed in Table 5, together with their exploitation strategy and key exploitation action to take.

Table 5 DigiBatt preliminary exploitation plan

Key exploitable result	Users	Exploitation route	Key exploitation actions
New battery testing domain ontology application.	Researchers, cell manufacturers, cell integrators, cell recyclers	Open-source release of software. Integration in key, widely used software packages e.g. MATLAB, Python, Julia	At least 1 public software release of ontology software on GitHub (or similar) Integration in at least 2 software languages out of Python, MATLAB, Julia and made available open-source.
Distributed semantic dataspace for storing and retrieving test data	Researchers, cell manufacturers, cell integrators, cell recyclers	Open-source release of software. Integration with existing and widely available digital infrastructure e.g. Gaia-X Accessible via key software packages which are integrated with the new ontology e.g. MATLAB, python, julia	At least 1 public software release of database software on GitHub (or similar) Publicly available example code / tutorials demonstrating software usage and integration with key infrastructure.

Battery cell digital twin framework	Researchers, cell manufacturers, cell integrators, cell recyclers	Open-source release of software. Adoption by research community with contributions from users (e.g. new interfaces to specific equipment, virtual testing models) Linking of digital twin with battery passport activities.	At least 1 public software release of digital twin software on GitHub (or similar) Publicly available example code / tutorials demonstrating integration with different equipment and virtual testing models. Key integrations publicly available to link digital twin models with battery passport data. At least 1 presentation of digital twin framework to stakeholders.
Physics-based lifetime modelling framework with accelerated parameterization	Researchers, cell manufacturers, cell integrators, cell recyclers	Open-source release of software. Adoption by research community with contributions from users (e.g. new virtual testing models, new methods for automatic parameterisation) Wider adoption by academic and industrial stakeholders via the increased use of digital twins developed in the project.	At least 1 public software release of lifetime modelling software on GitHub (or similar) Publicly available example code / tutorials demonstrating use of framework. At least 1 presentation of lifetime modelling framework to stakeholders.
Tools for intelligent design of testing protocols	Researchers, cell manufacturers, cell	Open-source release of software. Successful demonstration and use in 3 industrial settings.	At least 1 public software release on GitHub (or similar) Publicly available example code /

	integrators, cell recyclers	Wider adoption by industrial stakeholders	tutorials demonstrating use of intelligent testing design tools. At least 1 presentation of software and usage to stakeholders.
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9. Conclusions

Targeted and effective dissemination, exploitation and communication activities are essential to achieve maximum impact from the DigiBatt project. This document sets out the preliminary dissemination, exploitation and communication plan for the project. As the project progresses the effectiveness of communication activities will be assessed and the communication strategy will be updated accordingly. The document serves as a reference for all DigiBatt consortium members and will be used actively when undertaking dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.

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